

Studies on the Synthesis of Furocoumarins. Part-XXX. A Reinvestigation of Claisen Rearrangement of 7-Cinnamyloxy-4-methylcoumarin¹

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7-Cinnamyloxy-4-methylcoumarin on Claisen migration gave three products, *trans*-3,7-dimethyl-2-phenyl-2,3-dihydrofuro[2,3-*b'*]benzopyran 5[*H*]-one (1a), 7-hydroxy-4-methyl-8-(1'-phenylprop-1'-ene)coumarin (1e) and 7-hydroxy-4-methyl-6-(1'-phenylprop-2-ene)coumarin (1f). 1e and 1f on cyclisation with H₂SO₄ gave 2b and 3a respectively. 2a, 2b and 3a on dehydrogenation with either DDQ in dry benzene or Pd/C (10%) in diphenyl ether gave 4a, 4b and 5b respectively. In a similar way 2,5,9-trimethyl-3-phenylfuro[3,2-*b'*]benzopyran 7[*H*]-one (5c) was also synthesised. Structures of the compounds were confirmed by ¹H nmr spectra and *cis* and *trans*-stereochemistry of dihydrofurocoumarins was established by nOe difference spectra.

It is well established that substitution reaction and migration on 7-hydroxycoumarin ring system are regioselectively directed to C-8 position with traces of C-6 isomer. This regioselectivity is changed to C-6 position in the case of 7-hydroxy-3,4-dihydrocoumarin ring system². Pardanani and Trivedi³ observed that the Claisen rearrangement of 7-allyloxy-8-bromocoumarin in dimethylaniline gave 7-hydroxy-6-allylcoumarin, bromine being eliminated during the migration. Shah and Trivedi⁴ carried out the Claisen rearrangement of several 4-substituted-7-allyloxy-8-bromocoumarins and obtained 7-hydroxy-6-allyl-4-substituted-coumarins, thus establishing the regioselectivity of this reaction for C-5 isomer. Jain *et al.*⁵ carried out the Claisen rearrangement of 7-cinnamyloxy-4-methylcoumarin (1a) by refluxing it in *N,N*-dimethylaniline and obtained 7-hydroxy-4-methyl-8-(1'-phenylprop-1'-ene)coumarin (1e) as the only product. While Ahluwalia *et al.*⁶ carried out the same reaction by refluxing it for 24 h and isolated two products. One product was soluble in alkali, the same as that obtained by Jain *et al.*, and the other insoluble in alkali was assigned by the linear furocoumarin structure as either 4,4'-dimethyl-5'-phenylfuro(2',3':6,7)coumarin (5a) or 4,5'-dimethyl-4'-phenylfuro(2',3':6,7)coumarin (5b), the former being preferred on the basis of mechanism of migration and also on the basis of pmr studies, which is ambiguous. Moreover, the claim for the formation of linearly fused furan ring system is untenable on the following grounds: (i) the chemical shift of C₅-H and C₈-H as a broad singlet at δ 7.4 in the pmr spectrum is not consistent with the structure 5, the chemical shift of C₅-H and C₈-H in coumarin system is separated by at least δ 0.4, C₅-H appearing more downfield than the C₈-H and (ii) during Claisen rearrangement, the compound has undergone migration to C-6 followed by cyclisation and dehydrogenation in a

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1a; R₁=CH₂CH=CHPh, R₂=R₃=H
b; R₁=CH₂CH=CHPh, R₂=Br, R₃=H
c; R₁=CH₂CH=CHPh, R₂=I, R₃=H
d; R₁=CH₂CH=CHPh, R₂=CH₃, R₃=H
e; R₁=R₂=H, R₃=PhC=CHCH₃
f; R₁=R₂=H, R₃=PhCHCH=CH₂
g; R₁=R₂=H, R₃=PhC=CHCH₃
h; R₁=R₂=H, R₃=PhCHCH=CH₂

- 3
3a; R₁=H
b; R₁=CH₃

single step. The final step of dehydrogenation is very uncommon in the absence of any driving force in the reaction. Ahluwalia *et al.*⁴ could not assign the stereochemistry of dihydrofurocoumarins which are one of the products of the Claisen rearrangement.

In view of the above discrepancies, a reinvestigation of Claisen rearrangement of 7-cinnamyloxy-4-methylcoumarin (1a) was carried out under the identical conditions as stated by Ahluwalia *et al.*⁶. After usual work up, three products were isolated, two alkali-soluble and one alkali-insoluble. The alkali-soluble products were separated by preparative tlc, the major product was (1e) as assigned by Jain *et al.* and Ahluwalia *et al.*, and the minor alkali-soluble product (m.p. 192°) was assigned structure 7-hydroxy-6-(1'-phenylprop-2'-ene)-4-methylcoumarin (1f) on the basis of pmr spectrum which exhibited signals at δ (CDCl₃ + DMSO) 2.32 (3H, s, C₄-CH₃), 4.9-5.25 (3H, m, PhCHCH=CH₂ at C₆), 6.05 (1H, s, vinylic, C₃-H), 6.3 (1H, m, PhCH-CH=CH₂ at C₆), 6.85 (1H, s, C₈-H), 7.3 (5H, m, C₆H₅-CH=CH₂ at C-6), 7.45 (1H, s, C₈-H) and 9.8 (1H, exchangeable OH at C-7). The two singlets, at δ 6.85 and 7.45 for the two protons at C-8 and C-5 respectively, indicate that the migration has taken place in C-6 position. As the pmr spectrum does not show any signal for a methyl group the alternative structure (1f') is ruled out.

The alkali-insoluble product (m.p. 136°) was totally different from the product (m.p. 230-32°) which is reported by Ahluwalia and coworkers, and we failed to isolate it. It is assigned as *trans*-3,7-dimethyl-2-phenyl-2,3-dihydrofuro[2,3-*h*]benzopyran-5[*H*]-one (2a), an angular dihydrofurocoumarin on the basis of pmr spectra (CDCl₃ + DMSO) which exhibited signals at δ 1.6 (3H, d,

J 7 Hz, C₃-CH₃), 2.4 (3H, d, *J* 1.5 Hz, C₇-CH₃), 3.7 (1H, m, C₈-H), 5.3 (1H, d, *J* 7 Hz, C₂-H), 6.05 (1H, s, C₆-H), 6.8 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, C₈-H), 7.3 (5H, s, C₂-Ph) and 7.4 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, C₉-H). The formation of 2a can be explained as shown in Scheme 1. The Claisen rearrangement of 7-cinnamyloxy-4-methylcoumarin (1a) first yields the normal product (A) by [3,3]-shift, which undergoes cyclisation to form cyclopropane intermediate (C) through [1,5]-shift and it then opens

to give *trans*-3,7-dimethyl-2-phenyl-2,3-dihydrofuro[2,3-*h*]benzopyran-5[*H*]-one (2a). The *trans*-stereochemistry is confirmed by nOe studies. The doublet of O-CH-Ph at position C-2 was irradiated and the nOe was found in the Me group (7%) and also in the phenyl protons (10%) adjacent to it, indicating that C₂-H is *cis* to C₃-methyl group and *trans* to hydrogen on position C-3. Dehydrogenation of 2a with DDQ in dry benzene gave 2-phenyl-3,7-dimethylfuro[2,3-*h*]benzopyran-5[*H*]-one (4a).

The isomeric *cis*-2,7-dimethyl-3-phenyl-2,3-dihydrofuro[2,3-*h*]benzopyran-5[*H*]-one (2b) was obtained when 1e was triturated with concentrated H₂SO₄: δ (CDCl₃) 1.1 (3H, d, *J* 7 Hz, C₂-CH₃), 2.3 (3H, s, C₇-CH₃), 4.65 (1H, d, *J* 7 Hz, C₃-H), 5.2 (1H, m, C₂-H), 6.0 (1H, s, vinylic, C₆-H), 6.85 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, C₇-H), 6.95-7.25 (5H, m, C₆-Ph), 7.45 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, C₈-H). Pmr spectra showed multiplet for one proton at δ 5.2 and doublet for one proton at δ 4.7 indicating that CHCH₃ group is at C-2 and CHPh at C-3. Two doublets at δ 7.45 and 6.85 (*J* 9 Hz) for *ortho*-coupled protons at C-8 and C-9 indicate that it is an angular furocoumarin. The *cis*-stereochemistry in 2b was established by nOe studies. The doublet of CHPh at position C-3 was irradiated and the nOe was observed on the C₂-H and also on the proton of the phenyl ring. C₂-Me group showed no nOe at all, thus establishing that Me and Ph are *cis* to each other. This is further corroborated by upfield of methyl signal at δ 1.1 establishing that

the Me group is shielded by the phenyl ring when *cis* to one another. In case of **2a** the Me signal appeared downfield at δ 1.6 confirming *trans*-structure. Dehydrogenation of **2b** was carried out with DDQ in dry benzene to give the isomeric 2,7-dimethyl-3-phenylfuro[2,3-*h*]benzopyran-5[*H*]-one (**4b**).

In order to obtain linear furocoumarin, an isomer of the compound claimed by Ahluwalia *et al.*, the compound **1f** was prepared in large quantities by introducing bromine or iodine at C-8 position. Thus Claisen rearrangement of 7-cinnamyloxy-8-bromo or iodo-4-methylcoumarin in refluxing dimethylaniline gave **1f**. This when tritreated with 75% H_2SO_4 gave linear *trans*-2,5-dimethyl-3-phenyl-2,3-dihydrofuro[3,2-*g*]benzopyran-7[*H*]-one (**3a**): δ (CDCl₃) 1.5 (3H, d, *J* 7 Hz, C₂-CH₃), 2.3 (3H, s, C₅-CH₃), 4.15 (1H, d, *J* 7 Hz, C₃-H), 4.8 (1H, m, C₂-H), 6.05 (1H, s, C₆-H), 6.7 (1H, s, C₉-H), 7.09 (1H, s, C₄-H) and 7.2-7.4 (5H, m, C₈-Ph). The downfield shift of methyl groups at δ 1.5 indicates that the Me and Ph groups are *trans* to one another. This was dehydrogenated with Pd/C (10%) in refluxing diphenyl ether to give 2,5-dimethyl-3-phenylfuro[3,2-*g*]benzopyran-7[*H*]-one (**5b**): δ (CDCl₃) 2.45 (3H, s, C₂-CH₃), 2.55 (3H, s, C₅-CH₃), 6.2 (1H, s, C₆-H), 7.3 (1H, s, C₉-H), 7.4 (4H, s, C₈-Ph) and 7.6 (1H, s, C₄-H).

The other linear furanocoumarin 2,5,9-trimethyl-3-phenylfuro[3,2-*g*]benzopyran-7[*H*]-one (**5c**) was prepared by subjecting 7-cinnamyloxy-4,8-dimethylcoumarin to Claisen rearrangement in *N,N*-DMA to give 4,8-dimethyl-7-hydroxy-6-(1'-phenylprop-2-ene)-coumarin (**1g**) which was cyclised with H_2SO_4 to give *trans*-3-phenyl-2,5,9-trimethyl-2,3-dihydrofuro[3,2-*g*]benzopyran-7[*H*]-one (**3b**). *Trans*-stereochemistry is assigned on the basis that its pmr spectra showed doublet for C₂-CH₃ group at δ 1.6. **3b** on dehydrogenation with Pd/C (10%) in diphenyl ether furnished 3-phenyl-2,5,9-trimethylfuro[3,2-*g*]benzopyran-7[*H*]-one (**5c**).

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Pmr spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer (90 MHz) using TMS as internal standard.

7-Cinnamyloxy-4-methylcoumarins. General procedure: A solution of the appropriate 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (0.02 mol) in dry acetone (100 ml) was refluxed with potassium carbonate (15 g), cinnamyl chloride (0.02 mol) and a few crystals of potassium iodide on a water-bath for 5 h. It was worked up and the product obtained was treated with dilute alkali to remove the starting material. The product was crystallised from ethanol and benzene mixture (Table 1).

***trans*-3,7-Dimethyl-2-phenyl-2,3-dihydrofuro[2,3-*h*]benzopyran-5[*H*]-one (2a):** 7-Cinnamyloxy-4-methylcoumarin (1 g) was refluxed with *N,N*-dimethylaniline (5 ml) for 24 h at 210-20°. The mixture was then poured into cold dilute HCl and

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 1a-d

Compd. no.	Mol. formula	M p. °C	Yield %	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)	
				C	H
1a	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ O ₈	179	75	77.7 (78.0)	5.4 (5.5)
1b	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ O ₈ Br	192	70	61.2 (61.4)	3.8 (4.0)
1c	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ O ₈ I	210	75	55.0 (54.5)	4.0 (3.5)
1d	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₈	196	85	78.5 (78.4)	6.0 (5.8)

treated with solvent ether. The ethereal solution obtained was treated with dilute NaOH to separate the alkali-soluble and alkali-insoluble fractions. The alkali-insoluble fraction was evaporated and the residue crystallised from alcohol as colourless crystals (0.2 g), m.p. 136° (Found : C, 78.5 ; H, 5.4. C₁₉H₁₆O₈ requires : C, 78.1 ; H, 5.4%).

7-Hydroxy-4-methyl-8-(1'-phenylprop-1'-ene)coumarin (1e): The alkali-soluble fraction was acidified with dilute HCl and the separated product was filtered, dried and checked by tlc. It showed to be a mixture of two compounds which were separated by preparative tlc. The compound with higher *R_f* value was assigned structure (**1e**) and crystallised from dilute alcohol (0.3 g), m.p. 229° (lit. 223°) (Found : C, 77.8 ; H, 5.7. C₁₉H₁₆O₈ requires : C, 78.1 ; H, 5.4%); δ (CDCl₃+DMSO) 1.6 (3H, d, *J* 7 Hz, CHCH₃, C₈-CH₃), 2.35 (3H, s, C₄-CH₃), 6.05 (1H, s, vinylic, C₃-H), 6.45 (1H, m, CH₂CH=, C₈-H), 6.95 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, C₆-H), 7.1-7.3 (5H, m, C₈-Ph), 7.45 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, C₅-H) and 8.9 (1H, s, C₇-OH).

7-Hydroxy-4-methyl-6-(1'-phenylprop-2'-ene)coumarin (1f): The lower band was collected and extracted with ethanol, and the resulting solid was crystallised from dilute alcohol as colourless needles (0.1 g), m.p. 192° (Found : C, 77.8 ; H, 5.5. C₁₉H₁₆O₈ requires : C, 78.1 ; H, 5.4%).

The compound was also obtained by using 7-cinnamyloxy-8-bromo-4-methylcoumarin (**1b**) or 7-cinnamyloxy-8-iodo-4-methylcoumarin (**1c**). **1b** (2 g) was refluxed with *N,N*-dimethylaniline (15 ml) for 5 h. The mixture was worked up as described earlier and the product was recrystallised from dilute alcohol (0.3 g), m. p. 188°. **1c**, (2 g) was refluxed with *N,N*-dimethylaniline (15 ml) for 5 h. The mixture was worked up as usual and the product was crystallised from dilute alcohol (0.8 g), m.p. 190°. The m.p., m.m.p. and tlc were checked in both the cases.

3,7-Dimethyl-2-phenylfuro[2,3-*h*]benzopyran-5-*[H]*-one (4a): A mixture of **2a** (0.5 g) and DDQ (0.5 g) both in dry benzene, was refluxed on a water-bath for 8 h. The mixture was then filtered hot and the excess benzene was removed. On standing crystals separated out. The product was purified by column chromatography and crystallised from ethanol as pale pink needles (0.3 g), m.p. 187

(Found: C, 79.0; H, 4.9. $C_{19}H_{14}O_8$ requires: C, 78.5; H, 4.5%); δ ($CDCl_3$) 2.45 (3H, s, C_7-CH_3), 2.7 (3H, s, C_8-CH_3), 6.2 (1H, s, vinylic, C_6-H), 7.3–7.5 (5H, m, C_2-Ph) and 7.75 (2H, d, C_8-H , C_9-H).

cis-2,7-Dimethyl-3-phenyl-2,3-dihydrofuro[2,3-h]-benzopyran-5[H]-one (**2b**): A solution of **1e** (0.5 g) in 90% H_2SO_4 (1 ml) was heated on a water-bath for 5 min. The mixture was then poured in cold water. The resulting solid was washed with dilute NaOH and distilled water to remove the uncyclised starting compound and crystallised from benzene-alcohol mixture (10 : 1) as colourless needles (0.4 g), m.p. 154° (Found: C, 77.6; H, 5.2. $C_{19}H_{16}O_8$ requires: C, 78.0; H, 5.4%).

2,7-Dimethyl-3-phenylfuro[2,3-h]benzopyran-5[H]-one (**4b**): A mixture of **2b** (0.5 g) and an equivalent amount of DDQ (0.5 g), both in dry benzene, was refluxed on a water-bath for 50–60 h. The resulting solid was crystallised from benzene as pale pink needles (0.2 g), m.p. 226° (Found: C, 78.7; H, 4.9. $C_{19}H_{14}O_8$ requires: C, 78.5; H, 4.5%); δ ($CDCl_3$) 2.4 (3H, s, C_7-CH_3), 2.45 (3H, s, C_2-CH_3), 6.15 (1H, s, vinylic, C_6-H) and 7.3–7.5 (7H, m, C_8-Ph , C_8-H , C_9-H).

trans-2,5-Dimethyl-3-phenyl-2,3-dihydrofuro[3,2-g]-benzopyran-7[H]-one (**3a**): **1f** (0.5 g) was triturated with 75% H_2SO_4 in a water-bath for 5 min. The contents were then poured on crushed ice and the resulting solid was washed with dilute NaOH and crystallised from dilute alcohol as colourless needles (0.4 g), m.p. 154° (Found: C, 78.4; H, 5.6. $C_{19}H_{16}O_8$ requires: C, 78.0; H, 5.4%).

2,5-Dimethyl-3-phenylfuro[3,2-g]benzopyran-7-[H]-one (**5b**): A mixture of **3a** (0.4) and Pd/C (10%; 0.4 g) in diphenyl ether (6 ml) was refluxed for 6 h. The reaction mixture was filtered hot and the filtrate was cooled and diluted with petroleum ether (b.p. $40-60^\circ$; 5 ml). The resulting yellowish solid was crystallised from benzene as yellowish shining crystals (0.2 g), m.p. 185° (Found: C, 78.9; H, 4.8. $C_{19}H_{14}O_8$ requires: C, 78.5; H, 4.5%).

7-Hydroxy-4,8-dimethyl-6-(1'-phenylprop-2'-ene)-coumarin (**1g**): 7-Cinnamyloxy-4,8-dimethylcoumarin (**1d**; 2 g) was refluxed with *N,N*-dimethylaniline (15 ml) for 6 h. The mixture was then cooled and poured into ice-cold dilute HCl and extracted with solvent ether. The extract was washed with dilute NaOH. The alkaline extract on acidification with dilute HCl gave a solid which was crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether mixture as light yellow crystals (1.2 g), m.p. 168° (Found: C, 78.8; H, 6.0. $C_{20}H_{18}O_3$ requires: C, 78.4; H, 5.8%); δ ($CDCl_3$)

2.25 (6H, s, C_4-CH_3 , C_8-CH_3), 4.9–5.3 (2H, m, $PhCHCH=CH_2$ at C_6), 6.0 (1H, s, vinylic, C_3-H), 6.1–6.4 (1H, m, $PhCHCH=CH_2$ at C_6), 6.3 (1H, s, C_7-OH exchangeable with D_2O), 7.1 (1H, s, C_5-H) and 7.2 (5H, s, C_6-Ph).

trans-2,5,9-Trimethyl-3-phenyl-2,3-dihydrofuro[3,2-g]-benzopyran-7[H]-one (**3b**): Compound **1g** (0.5 g) was triturated with concentrated H_2SO_4 (0.5 ml) and heated on a water-bath for 5 min. The mixture was then cooled and poured onto crushed ice. The resulting solid was washed with dilute NaOH followed by distilled water and crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether mixture as colourless flakes (0.3 g), m.p. 159° (Found: C, 78.5; H, 6.2. $C_{20}H_{18}O_8$ requires: C, 78.4; H, 5.58%); δ ($CDCl_3$) 1.6 (3H, d, J 7 Hz, C_2-CH_3), 2.25 (3H, s, C_8-CH_3), 2.35 (3H, s, C_9-CH_3), 4.2 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, C_8-H), 4.7–4.9 (1H, m, C_2-H), 6.0 (1H, s, vinylic, C_6-H), 6.9 (1H, s, C_4-H) and 7.2–7.4 (5H, m, C_3-Ph).

2,5,9-Trimethyl-3-phenylfuro[3,2-g]benzopyran-7-[H]-one (**5c**): A mixture of **3b** (0.5 g) and Pd/C (10%; 0.5 g) in diphenyl ether (8 ml) was refluxed for 5 h. The mixture was then filtered hot, cooled and diluted with petroleum ether (5 ml). The resulting solid was washed with petroleum ether and crystallised from benzene as yellow shining needles (0.3 g), m.p. 192° (Found: C, 79.3; H, 5.6. $C_{20}H_{18}O_8$ requires: C, 78.9; H, 5.2%); δ ($CDCl_3$) 2.4 (3H, s, C_8-CH_3), 2.55 (3H, s, C_2-CH_3), 2.60 (3H, s, C_9-CH_3), 6.15 (1H, s, vinylic, C_6-H) and 7.4–7.5 (6H, m, C_3-Ph , C_4-H).

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References

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